

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

THE IMPORTANCE OF INVESTMENT IN HUMAN CAPITAL IN THE FORMATION OF AN INNOVATIVE ECONOMY

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Annotation. *The article examines the innovative economy and the role of human capital in its formation. The characteristics of human capital in improving the efficiency of investment activities are also studied.*

Keywords: *innovative economy, human capital, investment, investment activity, research and development, intellectual staff, operational efficiency, technological innovation, organizational innovation, marketing innovation, economic efficiency.*

The experience of developed countries shows that the creation of an innovative economy based on knowledge is a modern requirement. The strategic model of economic growth is to create new technologies based on intensive research, with which to ensure the competitiveness of the national economy by entering international markets that produce high-tech products. In addition, intellectual resources not only determine the prospects for economic development, but also serve as an indicator of the level of economic independence and prosperity of the country.

Today, the country attaches great importance to the accelerated development of innovations. In the medium term, one of the goals and priorities of state policy in the field of science is to "stimulate research and innovation, create effective mechanisms for the implementation of scientific and innovative achievements. establishment of specialized scientific and experimental laboratories, high-tech centers and technoparks at research institutes" [1]. In this regard, it is necessary to pay special attention to the financing of research and development, economic and financial incentives for innovation. As noted by the President Sh.M.Mirziyoev, "We need to attract investments in our country not only in the economy, but also in the field of scientific know-how" [3].

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One of the tools to determine the direction of innovative development in the context of the formation of an innovative economy is to identify the factors that increase the efficiency of human capital and invest in them. In an innovation-oriented economy, human capital is a key factor in increasing the efficiency of investment activities, and at the same time has its own characteristics compared to other capital. The development of innovations in the economy of the Republic, as well as the solution of a number of socio-economic tasks is directly related to increasing the efficiency of investments in human capital.

However, the ways of effective use of human resources are radically different from those of other resources, because in this case it provides an impact on people's motivation or their goals. The specificity of the motivation of intellectual workers is due to the fact that their goals and interests include economic and creative components. The motivation of intellectual workers depends on their efficiency, i.e. their ability to achieve the set goals. If his activity is ineffective, he will soon lose the desire to work and make a profit. In this regard, improving the efficiency of human capital use should be a priority for every state. The efficiency of an intellectual worker who embodies human capital is reflected in his ability to solve pressing tasks, and to increase the competitiveness of the economy, it is necessary to increase the labor efficiency of such employees [4].

Before describing the formation of an innovative economy, let us consider the following main features of an innovative economy:

- openness of the economy and society, the opportunity to participate as an equal partner in the international market of new technologies;
- The existence of a comprehensively competitive national innovation system and the creation of a complex of legal, financial and social institutions that ensure the interaction of educational, scientific, entrepreneurial and non-profit organizations;
- active participation of the state as the main coordinator of innovative development;
- Existence of high-tech and intellectual services;
- Opportunity to achieve a high level of competitiveness through the management of intellectual property.

One of the key elements in the development of an innovative economy is the national innovation system. This system will allow the country to achieve intensive economic growth through the use of effective mechanisms for obtaining the results of scientific, technical and innovative activities and their practical application. The

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competitiveness of the national innovation system can be determined by the following factors:

- level of attention to learning;
- the state of efficient use of human resources;
- conditions created for commercial processes;
- Creation of technological infrastructure, access to financial resources;
- Legislative, regulatory framework created by the government;
- The state of development of supply and service industries.

As a result of the competitiveness of the national innovation system, the following socio-economic development goals can be achieved:

- high quality of life;
- ecology and safety;
- efficiency and competitiveness of the economy.

The state of development of the innovation sector in the country can be analyzed on the basis of the following indicators: the share of domestic expenditures on research and development in GDP; the share of innovative products in the total volume of products sold in domestic and world markets; the share of enterprises engaged in innovative activities in the total structure of enterprises operating in the country.

It is known that innovation processes can be observed in three different directions:

- technological innovations;
- organizational innovations;
- marketing innovations.

In recent years, along with technological innovations, organizational and marketing innovations have become especially important in increasing production efficiency. However, the lack of timely or insufficient funding for innovation processes leads to a decline in the quality of innovations, which does not allow them to be implemented on a regular basis.

The main obstacles to the development of innovative activities in the country may be:

- lack of own free funds of the enterprise;
- lack or insufficiency of external sources of financing;
- Insufficient basic knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of innovation, low quality of human capital.

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Extensive work is being carried out in our country to create an innovation-oriented economy and create conditions for the widespread introduction of innovations.

One of the important steps in this direction was the establishment of a single state policy body in the field of innovation and scientific and technological development, the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, under which the Fund for Support of Innovative Development and Innovative Ideas was formed.

According to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 7, 2018 No PP-3698 "On additional measures to improve the mechanisms of innovation in industries and sectors of the economy" scientific equipment, components, consumables, reagents, software are exempted from customs duties, research organizations are exempted from all taxes and mandatory deductions for their main activities, the released funds are targeted for financial incentives for their employees [2]. In the era of scientific and technological progress and socio-economic development, human capital is becoming a necessary factor determining the future of the country. Human capital is the foundation of sustainable economic growth and the driving force of innovation.

International experience shows that investments in human capital, especially in education, are made in the long run from childhood and have a specific return on economic growth in the country. According to a study by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, an increase in the average statistical period of education for a certain qualification population by one year will increase the country's GDP by 3-6%. An increase of 1% in education will increase the country's GDP by 0.35%. But it should be borne in mind that investments in education are long-term investments, from which it is not right to expect rapid results, but such investments are essential for the successful development of the country.

According to the World Bank's study of the economies of 192 countries, 55% of economic growth is determined by human capital. According to experts, an increase in the duration of education in developed countries by one year will lead to an increase in GDP by 5-15%. For the sustainable development of the economy, it is first necessary to develop human capital. Countries around the world view spending on education development as a profitable investment, not a social one, meaning that investments in education are made not just for social necessity but for future benefits. Even in the face of global competition, countries that constantly increase their educational potential will win.

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Human capital has the same value as other material, natural and financial capital and needs to be renewed, modernized and developed. Human capital as an economic category differs between states in terms of efficiency and quality. These differences are identified through the United Nations Human Development Index. The productivity or efficiency of human capital is determined by the ratio of investments in it. This index is high in the most developed countries with a high quality of human capital, knowledge-oriented economy, and less than one for less developed countries. In countries with low labor productivity, this index is much lower. The coefficient of efficiency of human capital also determines the average labor productivity in value added industries. But the disadvantage of this index is that it does not take into account the quality of education, the health of the population.

It is necessary to determine the value and quality of human capital, taking into account science. Education and science are interrelated. In order to form an innovative economy and increase the efficiency of investments in human capital, it is necessary to:

- high level and quality of human capital, as well as increasing the amount of investment for its development;
- development of fundamental and applied sciences;
- increase the number of intellectual centers of technological development;
- increasing the share of innovation-oriented economy;
- increase efficiency in all spheres of human intellectual activity;
- development of effective state-supported innovation and venture systems;
- creating a favorable investment climate for the development of innovations and achieving high positions in investment ratings;
- Ensuring the integral integration of education, science and industry.

List of used literature:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the Action Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", Annex 1, paragraph 4.4.

2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 7, 2018 No PP-3698 "On additional measures to improve the mechanisms for the introduction of innovations in industries and sectors of the economy"

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